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**EFFECTS OF PACKAGING METHODS ON THE STORABILITY OF SMOKED
CATFISH UNDER AMBIENT CONDITIONS**

BY

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that, except for particular references which have been accordingly acknowledged, this project is the results of my own research and to the best of my knowledge it contains no material previously published by another person or material which has been accepted for the award of any other degree of any university.

DEDICATION

To our lovely parents and love ones, Mrs. Evelyn Nyarkoh (late), Mr. George Kuntu Blankson (PhD), Mr. John Kweku Achempim, Mrs. Cecilia Owusu and our supervisor who has been more than a father to us Ing. Dr Shadrack Kwadwo Amponsah for their prayers, support and encouragement.

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Our honest appreciation to our parents, whose advice, encouragement and financial support has seen us through our educational pursuit. We say God richly bless you all.

Finally, our gratitude goes to our course mates, project leads and friends for their special assistance during the practical phase of our research.

ABSTRACT

The preservation of smoked catfish, a widely consumed source of protein in Ghana, is crucial to maintaining its quality and safety during storage. This study investigates the effects of three different packaging methods; **No Packaging, Brown Paper Packaging, and Vacuum Seal Packaging** on the storability of smoked catfish under ambient conditions over a period of three months. Key parameters such as **color changes (Lightness (L*), Red-Green (a*), Yellow-Blue (b*) values), moisture content, aerobic plate count (CFU/g) and free fatty acids** were measured monthly to evaluate product quality and shelf life.

Results showed that vacuum-sealed packaging significantly reduced moisture loss, maintaining a stable moisture content of approximately 16% throughout the storage period, while fish with no packaging experienced a moisture increase from 6.8% to 16.8%. In terms of microbial load, vacuum seal packaging showed the lowest aerobic plate count, with values as low as 2.64×10^5 CFU/g, remaining well below the recommended microbial safety limit of 1×10^7 CFU/g. Color analysis indicated that vacuum-sealed samples experienced the least discoloration, while unwrapped fish showed the most notable changes in lightness (L*), redness (a*), and yellowness (b*).

In conclusion, vacuum seal packaging proved most effective in extending the storability of smoked catfish by minimizing moisture loss, microbial growth, and color changes under ambient conditions. The findings suggest that vacuum seal packaging should be considered for wider use in the Ghanaian smoked fish industry and other countries to improve product shelf life and quality.

TABLE OF CONTENT

DECLARATION.....	ii
DEDICATION.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	iv
ABSTRACT.....	v
TABLE OF CONTENT.....	vi
LIST OF FIGURES	ix
LIST OF TABLES.....	x
CHAPTER ONE.....	1
INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Background to the study	1
1.2 Problem Statement.....	3
1.3. Justification (Significance of this research)	4
1.4 Main Objective.....	5
1.5. Specific Objectives.....	5
CHAPTER TWO	6
LITERATURE REVIEW	6
2.1 Nutritional Value	6
2.2 Moisture Content	8

2.3 Preservation and Storability (Storage).....	8
2.4 Smoking (Methods and Effects)	9
2.5 Packaging.....	11
2.6 Ambient Conditions.....	12
2.7 PH	13
CHAPTER 3	14
MATERIALS AND METHODS.....	14
3.1 Study Area	14
3.2 Experimental Design.....	14
3.3 Sample Collection.....	15
3.4 Type of Fish	18
3.5 Habitat.....	18
3.6 Pre-preparation and smoking procedure	19
3.7. Packaging Methods.....	22
3.8. Storage Condition	22
3.9 Moisture Analysis.....	23
CHAPTER 4	25
RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.....	25
4.1. Results for Quality Assessment Tests for First Month.....	25
4.1.1. Microbial Test.....	25

4.1.2. MOISTURE CONTENT	28
4.1.3. Color Difference Test	31
4.1.4. Free Fatty Acid Test (FFA).....	35
4.2. Results From Quality Assessment Tests for Second Month.....	38
4.2.1. Microbial Test.....	38
4.2.2. Moisture content	40
4.2.3. Color Difference Test	43
4.2.4. FFA Test.....	45
4.3. RESULTS FROM QUALITY ASSESSMENT TESTS FOR THIRD MONTH	48
4.3.1. Moisture Content	48
4.3.3. Microbial Test.....	52
4.3.4. FFA Test.....	54
CHAPTER 5	57
CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	57
5.1. Conclusions.....	57
5.2. Recommendations.....	58
REFERENCES	59

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 3.1: View of the study area.....	14
Figure 3.2: Image of hoop net.....	16
Figure 3.3: Image of gill net	16
Figure 3.4: Fish mongers using electrofishing method for fish harvesting	17
Figure 3.5: Scoop Net	18
Figure 3.6: Images of different traditional smoking kilns	20
Figure 3.7: Image of improved metal smoking kiln at the cottage	20
Figure 3.11: Beginning of smoking process.....	21
Figure 3.9: End of smoking process	21
Figure 3.10: Samples preparation	21
Figure 3.8: Coiling of samples.....	21
Figure 3.14: No packaging sample	22
Figure 3.12: Brown Paper Packaging samples	22
Figure 3.13: Vacuum Packaging sample	22
Figure 3.15: Smoked packaged samples under mesh/net storage facility.	23
Figure 4.1: Recommended GSA Standard.....	27
Figure 4.2: Statistical representation of average test results obtained for first month moisture content.....	30
Figure 4.3 Statistical representation of average test results obtained for first month color difference	34
Figure 4.4: Statistical representation of FFA values.....	37
Figure 4.5: Statistical representation of average test results obtained	39
Figure 4.6: Second Month Average Moisture Content (%)	41

Figure 4.7: Statistical representation of average test results obtained for Second month color difference.	44
Figure 4.8: Statistical representation of FFA values.....	47
Figure 4.9: Third Month Average Moisture Content (%)	49
Figure 4.10: Statistical representation of average test results obtained for third month color difference	51
Figure 4.11: Statistical representation of average test results obtained for the 3rd month.....	53
Figure 4.12: Statistical representation of FFA values.....	56

LIST OF TABLES

Table 4.1: Aerobic Plate Count..... 26

Table 4.2: Computation of test results from KNUST food science lab on microbial load..... 26

Table 4.3: Statistical representation of average test results obtained 27

Table 4.4: Computation of results from KNUST food science lab..... 29

Table 4.5: Computation of average result..... 30

Table 4.6: Computation of results for the color parameters in the vacuum seal packaging 32

Table 4.7: Computation of results for the color parameters in the brown paper packaging..... 33

Table 4.8: Computation of results for the color parameters in the no packaging (control)..... 33

Table 4.9: Oil weight of samples..... 35

Table 4.10: Titre values 36

Table 4.11: Computation of test results from KNUST food science lab on microbial load..... 38

Table 4.12: Computation of results from KNUST food science lab..... 40

Table 4.13: Computation of average results 41

Table 4.14: Computation of results for the color parameters in the vacuum seal packaging 43

Table 4.15: Computation of results for the color parameters in the brown paper packaging..... 43

Table 4.16: Computation of results for the color parameters in the no paper packaging 44

Table 4.17: Titre values 45

Table 4.18: Oil weight of samples..... 46

Table 4.19: Computation of results from KNUST food science lab..... 48

Table 4.20: Computation of average results 48

Table 4.21: Computation of results for the color parameters in the vacuum seal packaging 50

Table 4.22: Computation of results for the color parameters in the brown paper packaging..... 50

Table 4.23: Computation of results for the color parameters in the vacuum seal packaging 51

Table 4.24: Computation of test results from KNUST food science lab on microbial load..... 52

Table 4.25: Titre values	54
Table 4.26: Oil weight of samples.....	55

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

Catfishes are one of the world's most economically important group of fresh and brackish water fishes. Catfishes are initially reared indoors from day 1 to 2 weeks and they are then transferred to fertilized outdoor ponds where they either feed on natural zooplankton or compound feeds (Gisbert et al., 2017). It has been reported that catfish consumption account for about 17% of animal protein consumption in Africa and this could mean that fish farming is a vibrant and dynamic commercial sector in Africa, ripe with investment and employment opportunities (USAID,2014). It's nutritional value is well suited to human dietary needs.

However, the gap between the demand and supply of catfish is widening due to increase in population. In view of this, despite the high level of catfish production in Africa, the demand for catfish is still higher than the supply in the market could meet up with (Shehu,2014). According to USAID (2014), consumer demand in Nigeria was reported to be 2.66 million metric tons which was met only in part by imports of about 740,000 metric tons that same year. Less than 50% of the demand for catfish is currently being met by local supply.

With the rate of population growth in Africa, demand is likely to be on the increase for the consumption of fish in the future. In catfish production, consumers' preferences and interests are always of the foremost importance to the aquaculturists, leading to an improvement of aquacultural techniques and producing food, which is considered by the consumer as attractive and acceptable. In view of this, the catfish consumer constitutes a major link between the demand and supply. The knowledge of consumers' preferences might increasingly contribute in the improvement of the terms of production, fish distribution and the quality of their processed products (Garnier et al., 2003).

However, in as much as we trying to meet up with demand as said earlier, the little supply on the market is been lost due to postharvest losses. Postharvest losses of fish take place in the fish value

chain in various degrees or extent. This results in general loss of income to the people involved in the value chain and also loss in availability of fish as food; hence that represent a major food security concern in Africa, where many people are food insecure (Signa, 2014). In the tropics, catfish spoils within 12 – 24 hours after harvesting depending on the specie, handling, method of capture, etc. (Obasohan et al., 2012). All the factors contribute to the postharvest losses. Chemical breakdown of fat, protein and water contents contribute to quick spoilage of catfish (Daramola et al., 2013). Postharvest losses has led to catfish wastage and spoilage which has been recognized as a significant constraint in achieving the much-desired self-sufficiency in food and fibre production in Africa (FAO, 2000). Postharvest losses of fish in general exceeds those of any other commodity, often surpassing 50% of the landed catch (FAO, 2000). Significant quality is also lost through the absence of adequate technology and expertise to prevent losses in many tropical countries (Adeyemi et al., 2013).

Packaging plays a crucial role in preserving the freshness and quality of smoked catfish by providing protection against external factors such as oxygen exposure, moisture loss, and microbial contamination. Vacuum packaging has emerged as a promising technique for enhancing the storability of smoked catfish. By removing air from the package and creating a vacuum seal, vacuum packaging minimizes oxygen exposure, thereby slowing down oxidation processes and reducing the risk of spoilage. Additionally, vacuum-sealed packages help retain moisture within the fish, preventing dehydration and preserving its texture and juiciness (Lekjing, et al., 2019). In addition to vacuum packaging, other packaging methods, such as modified atmosphere packaging (MAP), polyethylene bags, and plastic wrap, are commonly employed for storing smoked catfish. These methods offer varying degrees of protection and preservation, depending on factors such as packaging material permeability, sealing techniques, and storage conditions. For example, MAP involves replacing the air inside the package with a specific gas mixture, typically carbon dioxide and nitrogen, to inhibit microbial growth and delay spoilage (Zhu, et al., 2018). The choice of packaging method can significantly influence the storability and quality of smoked catfish. Studies have shown that improper packaging can lead to reduced shelf life, off-flavors, and texture deterioration. Therefore, optimizing packaging techniques is essential for maintaining the freshness and extending the shelf life of smoked catfish products (Ojokoh, et al., 2020).

Maintenance of high-quality fish is therefore call for adequate, effective and affordable preservative technique to enhance preservation and to curb for the postharvest losses which includes spoilage and wastage, and add value to the smoked catfish products, various preservation techniques are employed. These preservative techniques include chilling, freezing, canning, drying, salting, the additions of acids to chemically control microbial loads and smoking (Kumolu et al., 2010). However, smoking is the most popular method of processing catfish (Olalekan et al., 2019). Freezing on the other hand, has an aim of combining shelf-life extension with maintenance of sensory and nutritional characteristics (Jones, 2019).

1.2 Problem Statement

Microbial spoilage is one of the causes of quality deterioration of smoked catfish during storage even under ambient conditions (Salaudeen, M.M and Osibona, A.O 2018). Storage duration of smoked catfish depends on the smoking technique(s) and its Packaging technique(s) adopted.

Due to growth of bacteria and formation of toxins of unsmoked catfish, this basically results in huge postharvest losses to the farmers. Postharvest losses of catfish have reduced its economic value to catfish farmers and this has resulted in a loss in the general consumption and the use of catfish even for medicinal purposes. Also, local farmers run at losses because of their poor packaging techniques which tends to have huge problem during their storage stage.

Despite the importance of smoked catfish as a preserved product, there is a shortage of comprehensive literature addressing the impact of various packaging methods on its storability under ambient conditions

These knowledge gaps hinder efforts to develop effective strategies to mitigate post-harvest losses and enhance the economic viability of catfish farming operations.

1.3. Justification (Significance of this research)

Because of the economic value of catfish, it has become very meaningful to consider the packaging techniques of smoked catfish and the effects each of the packaging methods has on the storability

of catfish under ambient conditions. This research will be focused on using smoke to halt the formation of toxins and reduce the growth of bacteria due to lower water activity as a result of smoking in addition to salting and drying which creates a physical barrier (Hilaire Womeni,2012).

It's critical to comprehend how different packaging techniques affect how long smoked catfish keeps for a number of reasons. First of all, in order to satisfy consumer demand, it is crucial to maintain the quality of smoked catfish and increase its shelf life due to its substantial cultural and gastronomic significance. Also, improper packaging techniques can result in food waste and financial losses for distributors, retailers, and manufacturers. We can maximize the use of priceless seafood resources and reduce food waste by refining packing procedures. Furthermore, by guaranteeing a consistent supply of nutrient-dense seafood products, improving the storability of smoked catfish also helps to promote food security, by lessening the environmental impact of food production and delivery, solving packaging difficulties is consistent with sustainability aims. In the end, funding studies on smoked catfish packaging techniques helps the environment, producers, and consumers all around, fostering a more robust and sustainable seafood sector.

The salt content, duration and temperature of smoking, density of smoke and component of smoke affects the presence and composition of spoilage and pathogenic microflora of the smoked product (Kolodziejska et al., 2002) and that's what we want to achieve at the end of this research.

1.4. Main Objective

The major objective and motive of this research is to observe, elaborate, assess and study the effects the packaging methods has on the storability of smoked catfish (*Clarias garienpinus*) under ambient conditions.

1.5. Specific Objectives

This research sought to:

A. Compare the commonly used traditional and newly acquired packaging methods of smoked catfish.

B. Specifically study the effects of the packaging methods on the smoked catfish taking the storability into consideration under same ambient conditions.

C. Add to the literature on the perception of people about smoked catfish.

D. Assess the efficiency of smoking as a processing and preservation method.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Nutritional Value

Catfish has traditionally been used as the main supplement of vitamins and animal protein in many impoverished Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries. The most unique nutritional features of catfish meal are high levels of protein (60%) combined with Calcium (8%) and phosphorus (4.2%) (Dale, 2009). Furthermore, catfish meat is thought to be healthier than animal meat due to its lower cholesterol content (Rario, 2015). For starters, catfish contains many daily recommended vitamins including omega 3 and omega 6, healthy fats that serves important functions such as improving heart health and reducing blood pressure.

Another fundamental vitamin that you can get from consuming catfish is B-12 which supports the functionality of Red Blood Cells and overall brain health. It has little fat and is low in carbohydrates (Smith, 2012). It is also a versatile fish that may be prepared in various ways, such as broiled, fried, blackened, grilled and stir fried (Lee, 2016). Catfish is generally consumed fresh and is relatively cheap in a country like Turkey.

The inclusion of catfish in the diets of people such as pregnant and nursing mothers, infants and pre-school children because it contains polyunsaturated fatty acids which are essential in the development of the brain and nervous system (Steffens & Wirth, 2007). However, there could be high risk of heavy metal bioaccumulation, such as mercury (which is accumulated by the fishes during industrial pollution of streams and oceans (Smith, 2012; Guedenon, 2012). Therefore USAID (2011) recommended that pregnant women and nursing mothers should follow dietary guidelines of 8 oz per week of low mercury for adults to minimize risks of cancer.

It is desirable to increase the proportion of the catfish used for human consumption, because it is an important source of cheap, high-quality protein in developing countries such as Turkey. Smoked catfish may have some appeal as a specialty catfish product. To satisfy consumer demand, it is necessary to produce good-quality and safe smoked fish products.

Since catfish are composed of perishable nutrients, packaging and storage should be kept to a minimum with adequate storage conditions provided as to prevent deteriorative changes occurring through oxidative and microbial infestation. Pathogenic organisms has so many ways of entering processed foods (which in this case, is a smoked catfish), it can be introduced during processing from the environment, air, water, unsanitary utensils, equipments, unclean hands and sewage (FDA,2001).

WHO (2014) reported that dried catfish of 15% moisture content or less could inhibit microbial growth. The moisture content of smoked catfish usually fluctuates between 10.0% and 18.0% during storage periods (Salaudeen, 2018). These fluctuations which occurs during storage period is as a result of differences in relative humidity and temperature of storage conditions.

Udochukwu et al., (2016) reported decrease in microbial loads of smoked catfish as compared to fresh catfish of the same species from open markets as a result of smoking effects. Nutritional wise, increase in microbial loads over time was also reported by Ikutegbe and Sikoki (2014). FAO (2016) reported *Penicillium sp* and *Aspergillus niger* as the most common fungi associated with smoked catfish.

To add up, a study conducted by Salaudeen, M.M and Osibona, A.O (2018) showed a general decline in microbial safety of smoked catfish products. The nutritional value and shelf life of stored smoked catfish depends on the smoking technique, storage conditions and duration of storage. Therefore, to prevent and minimize health risks to consumers, smoked catfish should be hygienically handled, properly stored for short storage period.

2.2 Moisture Content

It has been reported that increase in moisture content is due to relative humidity differences in storage containers. Moisture content of catfish can be determined by difference in weight of the homogenized samples before and after smoking (within a specific time frame) in an oven at a determined temperature (AOAC, 2009). This led to a hydrogen ion (pH) change in the freshly smoked catfish which fluctuated during the storage period.

Moisture content is a determinant of the quality of smoked catfish product. Drying is applied to lower the moisture content of catfish to a level that can prevent the growth of mould and infestation of microorganisms thus minimizes microbial degradation. In comparing 2 different studies, the moisture content values of the initial and controlled samples of research conducted by Magawata and Musa (2015) were higher than the findings of Olayemi et al., (2011) who opined that the recommended safe moisture content of smoked catfish is between 6-8% because, the moisture content of their experiment was at a safe level of 7.3%. The disparity was attributed to the extent of dryness as well as the smoking duration and type of smoking used.

2.3 Preservation and Storability (Storage)

Storage bowls, bamboo baskets, net storage, iron baskets, etc. are few of the storage containers or facilities. Fish preservation and processing is carried out mainly to slow down or prevent the enzymatic, microbial and chemical deterioration of fresh fish. Lack of storage facilities can be responsible for the susceptibility of fish to damage and spoilage.

Under poor storage, numerous pathogenic agents isolated from different types of fish are able to grow and produce their toxic secondary metabolites which are retained in fish-flesh. Christianah et al., (2010) also attributed occurrence of *Penicillium sp* and *Aspergillus niger* to poor processing, handling and re-absorption of moisture during storage.

2.4 Smoking [Methods and Effects]

A number of processing techniques such as chilling, freezing, canning, drying, salting, smoking and fermentation are employed by fish processors in Africa. However, smoking is the affordable and widely used method for fish preservation in Nigeria, Ghana and other West African countries (Adeyemi et al., 2013; Nyarko, 2011). It is the most common and practicable method of preservation (Olalekan et al., 2019). Smoking involves the application of heat to remove water and inhibit bacterial and enzymatic action on fish. In addition, Cooperative and Extension Service (2012) observed that smoking fish for a short time offers the best quality product (if for canning).

Smoking is a traditional method of preserving fish in many places of the world (both rural and urban dwellers), although today it's acceptance in developed countries is based primarily upon the sensory characteristics it imparts to the product. In preserving catfish by smoking, water activity is lowered to a point where the activity of spoilage microorganisms is inhibited (Akinola, 2020). In addition, smoking increases the shelf life of fish as a result of the combined effects of dehydration, antimicrobial and antioxidant activities of several of the smoke constituents (Doe, 2006). Smoke determines the color which is one of the qualities that attracts consumers. The color of smoked catfish is relatively not independent on the method as well as the type of wood or agricultural waste used in smoking the fish (Aremu et al., 2013).

It is an important processing method aimed at reducing postharvest losses and it has the effect of imparting pleasant flavor to the product besides the preservative effects of smoking. Smoking is a dominant catfish processing method globally and this is due to the fact that it is affordable and improves the organoleptic properties of the final product (Obasohan et al., 2012). Smoking preserves fish by cooking and depositing natural wood-smoke chemicals like tars, phenols and aldehydes all of which have powerful bactericidal action and prevents the growth of other microorganisms on the flesh of the fish (Aremu et al., 2013). Processors of smoked catfish adopts different handling methods which have effect on the quality of the final product. According to Omojowo et al (2008) salting, addition of vinegar as well as the type of wood used for the smoking fire have significant contribution to the quality of smoked catfish. The amount and intensity of smoke will help determine the heat input.

However, smoking may present some potential health issues to smoked fish consumers. The process of smoking fish involves the use of sodium, sometimes through curing before smoking. Catfish is marinated in brine or packed with salt and can trigger high blood pressure in high doses (Nunmer & Andress, 2008). In addition, improper fish curing before smoking presents the risks of food poisoning that can lead to bacterial infection, listeriosis (food contamination by bacteria) in the consumer and bacterial or fungal growth on the fish (Steck et al., 2007).

A study conducted by Olalekan et al., (2019), shows that smoking methods has effects on quality indices, microbial quality and consumer acceptance of smoked catfish products. Smoking increases the Free Fatty Acids of catfish. Hot and cold smoking were found to be the suitable treatment methods for catfish because they gave it a high nutritive value as compared to other

smoking methods (Noel et al., 2013). There was no yeast and mould growth in the freshly smoked catfish as at day 12 (Joanne et al., 2008). Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) are widespread environmental contaminants representing an important group of carcinogens that have been detected in smoked catfish. This work investigated the effects of fish smoking methods considered accounted for differences in smoked catfish content of 16 PAHs. The results revealed traditional methods of smoking had 7 genotoxic PAHs. Traditionally smoked catfish were 18-24 times higher than those measured by modern smoking methods. Risk assessment conducted using a benzo[a]pyrene carcinogenic and mutagenic toxicity equivalent factors (TEF and MEF respectively) showed low risk (2.01×10^{-8} to 2.86×10^{-8} and 1.09×10^{-8} to 1.83×10^{-8} , respectively for **carcinogenicity and mutagenicity**) associated with consuming smoked catfish and below the USEPA guideline (1.0×10^{-5}) for potential cancer risk. Mean hazard indexes were below 1 (below an acceptable cumulative threshold) ranging from 1.43×10^{-6} to 9.96×10^{-8} . A significantly high accumulation of PAHs was found in smoked catfish as compared to non-smoked samples. The study indicated that there were no adverse health effects of PAHs content on consumers of smoked catfish species but levels of PAHs present in smoked catfish prepared using **traditional methods** may pose elevated cancer risks if consumed at high consumption rates over many years (Shehu et al., 2015).

2.5 Packaging

We have emphasized already on the fact that smoking and drying are major methods of processing and preserving fish in Ghana. However, traditional packaging methods using vacuum seal, cartoons, basket, jute, brown paper, mat bags and no packaging as control are the most common but offer little protection against external agents and has been a major challenge (Olayemi, 2012). There is dearth of information on the developments of appropriate fish packaging thereby limiting fishery preservation to small scale businesses.

Some of the composite packaging methods are; Polyethylene-Cardboard (PC), Cardboard-Polyethylene (CP), Polyethylene-Cardboard-Polyethylene (PCP), Polyethylene-Paper (PPa), Paper-Polyethylene (PaP), Polyethylene-Paper-Polyethylene (PPaP) and Polyethylene as control.

These packaging materials especially Polyethylene-Paper-Polyethylene practically maintained better quality attributes of stored catfish. Polyethylene-Paper-Polyethylene practically performed better in resistance to moisture and oil migration. It also proved high protein retention and better sensory attributes. The packaging material maintained the quality attributes of the stored smoked catfish. It was effective in extending the shelf life of smoked catfish. This was a report based on an experiment that was done by Folorunsho Olayemi, Michael Omodara & Olufemi Peters (2015).

2.6 Ambient Conditions

In spite of the nutritional importance of catfish, it is highly perishable especially in hot climatic regions where average temperature is warm enough to enhance proliferation of mycodeteriogens. The most important environmental factors governing the storage and shelf life of catfish are ambient temperatures and humidity. The factors dictate the rate at which chemical and microbial changes take place (Daramola, 2007). In the high ambient temperatures of the tropics, spoilage could occur within 12 to 20 hours depending on species, method of catch and chemical composition, while deterioration takes about 2 to less than 6 days in cooler climates (Olayemi et al., 2015). Ambient temperature directly and indirectly encourages the growth of moulds.

During storage, mould contaminants used to compromise ambient temperature and appear invisible on smoked-dried catfish. The conditions vary widely including; quality of fish at the time of smoking, smoking temperature and duration, salt content and drying time (Nickelson et al., 2001). Odu et al., (2004) stated that warm humidity and environmental temperatures can facilitate growth and succession of moulds in smoked-dried catfish at storage stage. The occurrence of these moulds suggests that the heat supplied during smoke-drying might not be adequate to kill the mould contaminants, and this may negatively enhance other unfavourable factors that can lead to mycodeterioration of smoked-dried catfish.

2.7 PH

The pH level of water can be detected using pH sensors. Nester et al., (2010) reported that a high pH favors microbial growth and that most bacteria will grow best at neutral pH, although they can still tolerate ranges from pH 5 (acidic) to pH 8 (basic). However, the water quality can decrease due to unstable pH conditions and temperature changes (Irfan et al., 2022). In this case, periodic monitoring is necessary to maintain a stable pH. Water quality that meets the standards will provide comfortable conditions for catfish.

Actually, catfish can still adapt to water of pH 9, but in this condition the growth of catfish will be hampered. A pH that is too low can cause fish to be lazy to move, excrete excess mucus and can cause death; if the pH is too high, it can cause stress to catfish and slow catfish development (Irfan et al., 2022). Under conditions of pH below neutral, i.e., acidic, fungi and bacteria can easily breed. On the other hand, when the pH is above neutral, catfish can live well which means they can live in an alkaline pond water atmosphere. Therefore, if the pH of the water in the pond becomes acidic, the activities carried out are to increase the alkaline conditions in the pond water so that the atmosphere of the pond becomes neutral.

CHAPTER 3

Materials and Methods

3.1 Study Area

This project was conducted at the Cottage of Council for Scientific and Industrial Research – Crop Research Institute (Fumesua Campus) along the KNUST to Ejisu Main Road.

Fig 3.1: view of the study area

3.2 Experimental Design

The study was designed to assess the influence of three packaging methods (No Packaging, Brown Paper Packaging, and Vacuum Seal Packaging) on the storability of smoked catfish under one storage condition. (Ambient temperature). The more appropriate experimental design in this case becomes: **Completely Randomized Design.**

Microsoft Excel (LTSC Standard 2021) was used for descriptive statistics and plotting of graphs. To obtain more accuracy in this research, three reps were used.

Packaging Method (PM): -Vacuum seal packaging

-Brown paper packaging

-Control (No packaging)

2. Storage condition (SC): - Ambient

Total samples= (PM Levels x SC levels x Reps)

$$= (3 \times 1 \times 3) = 9 \text{ treatments per month}$$

Total samples for 3 months = 9 per month x 3 months = **27 total samples**.

3.3 Sample Collection

All twenty-seven (27) samples of fresh catfish were obtained from fish pond 1 in order to obtain homogeneity among the samples, this made the variability among the samples negligible. The 27 samples each had a maximum weight of 1kg and minimum of 0.6kg which meets the criteria for harvesting matured African Catfish at the cottage.

There are numerous methods of sampling catfish from ponds which includes;

- **Hoop net:** Hoop nets are commonly used to sample catfish in river systems and small impoundments (Brown, 2009). Traditionally, hoop nets produce low catch rates.

Fig 3.2: Image of hoop net

- **Gillnetting:** Gill nets are most commonly used in fish reservoirs. They are cost effective and easy to use (Miranda, 2009). The mesh sizes are designed to allow fish to get only their head through the netting but not their body. The spectrum of catchable fish using this method is very broad (unlimited) in a sense that fish of all sizes can be caught.

Fig 3.3: Image of gill net

- **Scoop net fishing:** Also known as dip net, is designed to gently and securely capture fish without causing damage to the fish or the net. Scoop net means a type of fishing net consisting of a bag of mesh material kept open with a rigid frame and manipulated by a rigid handle that is designed to be used by a single person unaided by any mechanical device. Scoop nets are mainly used in artisanal fisheries. scoop nets in whatever form, used as direct fishing gear, will be operated in a different manner by men, women and children.

The usual method is a scooping movement when wading in breast-deep water. Catching by scooping demands rapid action for successful results.

Fig 3.4: image of scoop net

- **High Frequency Electrofishing:** It involves the application of electric current to the water through a pole or boom placed into the water, stunning fish. The stunned fish float to the surface where fish mongers collect them in nets. Fish mongers usually conducts electrofishing from boats but can also use a backpack unit.

Fig 3.5: fish mongers using electrofishing method for fish harvesting

In this particular research, we opted for **scoop net** for our sampling procedure.

Fig 3.6: project student harvesting samples with scoop net

3.4 Type of Fish

The focus of this study is on African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*), a species known for its resilience, rapid growth rate, and significant aquaculture potential. African catfish is a popular choice in many regions due to its high protein content, firm texture, and mild flavor. It is widely consumed and often smoked to enhance its shelf life and flavor profile. Rearing of catfish ranges from extensive, semi-intensive and intensive. Their feeding protocols also vary with species and geographical locations upon which they find themselves in.

3.5 Habitat

African Catfishes are natives to freshwater environments in Africa but has been introduced to other parts of the world due to its commercial value. Their production is increasing from intensive pond culture or in heated or geothermal waters (Otomar Linhart et al.,2002)

3.6 Pre-preparation and smoking procedure

Mostly, the smoking is done using traditionally built smoking kilns which require a lot of firewood, time and labor to smoke the fish. In order to reduce problems associated with the traditional smoking and other losses, we used a well improved metal smoking kiln which was constructed by the smoking department at the Cottage.

- Appreciable amount of local salt poured on the 27 freshly harvested samples which 17.3kg to naturally kill them by reacting with the slimy secretions from the catfish which creates an uncomfortable environment for the fish.
- The use of table salt has numerous advantages over the traditional method of nof cutting through the fish which includes:
 - Less time consuming.
 - Preserves the natural contents of the fish.
 - Delay in perishability.

- After 2-hours, the salted dead samples were thoroughly washed and coiled for the smoking process to start.
- The smoking process lasted for 23-hours at a smoking temperature of 101.6°C using a thermometer gun.
- Cooling process was initiated for 6-hours after smoking

Fig 3.7: images of different traditional smoking kilns

Fig 3.8: image of improved metal smoking kiln at the cottage

Fig 3.9: Samples preparation

Fig 3.10: Coiling of samples

Fig 3.11: Beginning of smoking process

Fig 3.12: End of smoking process

3.7. Packaging Methods

Three packaging methods were considered; no packaging, brown paper packaging and vacuum seal packaging

- **No Packaging:** Smoked catfish samples were left exposed to the environment without any form of packaging.
- **Brown Paper Packaging:** Smoked catfish samples were wrapped in food-grade brown paper.
- **Vacuum Seal Packaging:** Smoked catfish samples were vacuum-sealed using a commercial vacuum sealing machine with high-barrier vacuum bags.

Fig 3.13: No packaging samples

fig 3.14: Vacuum seal packaging

fig 3.15: Brown paper packaging

3.8. Storage Condition

Ambient Condition: Samples were stored at room temperature (approximately 25-30°C) in a controlled environment to simulate typical ambient storage conditions.

Fig 3.16: Smoked packaged samples under mesh/net storage facility.

3.9 Moisture Analysis

After smoking and cooling, all steaks of the smoked catfish were packed in one basket, and kept in the preferred packaging materials at room temperature for some three (3) months. Steak samples obtained after pre-smoking soaking treatments and after smoking followed by storage for three (3) months were subjected to microbiological and physicochemical analyses. Moisture content was determined by using the moisture oven at Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (KNUST) food science lab and the derived initial and final weights using the formula **Moisture Content (%) = [(Initial Mass - Final Mass) / Initial Mass] × 100.**

The expected final moisture content of our study is expected to either agree with or opine to the moisture content of the experiment that was done by Olayemi et al., (2011) who agreed that the safe moisture content of a smoked catfish sample should be between 6-8% or find a common ground with the values obtained by Magawata and Musa (2015) which were higher than 8%.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 RESULTS FOR QUALITY ASSESMENT TESTS FOR 1st MONTH

4.1.1. MICROBIAL TEST

The purpose of this parameter was to determine the Colony Forming Units per gram (CFU/g) of smoked catfish stored under three different packaging methods: No Packaging, Brown Paper Packaging, and Vacuum Seal Packaging. The aerobic plate count method was employed to assess the microbial load, which is a critical parameter for evaluating the safety and quality of food products. The acceptable standard for smoked fish is less than 1×10^7 CFU/g, which corresponds to a logarithmic value of less than 7.00 log CFU/g.

Sample Preparation and Inoculation (For enumeration either by pour or Spread plate)

1. 10g of test sample was transferred into a 90 ml of buffered peptone water to make 10^{-1} dilution.
2. From the first dilution, serial decimal dilutions were prepared by transferring 1ml of 10^{-1} dilution into a tube containing 9ml of diluent
3. The appropriate dilutions of the sample were inoculated into media by spreading 0.1ml of the inoculum or pipetting 1ml of inoculum (pour plate) and adding media tempered to about 50°C.
4. Plates were incubated upside down in an incubator set to respective
5. temperatures for bacterial plates and upright for fungal plates (yeasts and moulds).

4.1.1.1. SAMPLE METHODOLOGY

Analytical unit of sample used: 10g in 90 ml of Buffered Peptone Water

BPW: 0.1 % Buffered Peptone Water (0.1g in 100 ml)

PCA: Plate Count Agar (4.375g in 250ml distilled water). *Search for Oxoid + Name of media (For eg. Plate Count Agar) for detailed directions on preparations.*

Calculation of Test results:

$$\text{CFU/g} = \frac{\text{Number of colonies} * \% \text{Confirmed colonies}}{\text{Dilution Factor} * \text{Volume of inoculum used}}$$

TEST	PARAMETERS	INOCULUM USED	REFERENCE
Aerobic Plate Count	BPW/PCA @ 35°C for 48h	0.5 ml (Pour plate)	Oxoid - PCA

NB: CFU/g – Colony forming unit per gram of sample

4.1.1.2. TEST RESULTS

MICROBIOLOGICAL DATA - catfish							
TEST	Sample Name	Sample ID	Counts in CFU/ml	LOG CFU	Average		Stdev
			CFU/g		CFU/g	LOG CFU/g	
APC	No packaging Sample 3	NPS3	1.62×10 ⁷	7.21	9.26×10 ⁶	7.03	0.99
	No packaging Sample 3	NPS3	1.78×10 ⁷	6.85			
	Vacuum sealed Sample 3	VPS3	6.80×10 ⁴	4.83	2.64×10 ⁵	5.25	0.59
	Vacuum sealed Sample 3	VPS3	4.60×10 ⁵	5.66			
	Brown paper Sample 3	BPS3	6.60×10 ⁶	6.82	6.60×10 ⁶	6.82	0.00
	Brown paper Sample 3	BPS3	6.60×10 ⁶	6.82			

Fig 4.1: Computation of test results from KNUST food science lab on microbial load

4.1.1.3. LIMIT/SPECIFICATION ACCORDING TO GHANA STANDARDS

AUTHORITY'S GS955:2019

Test	Limit in CFU/g	Limit in LOG CFU/g
Aerobic plate count (APC)	1×10^7	7.00

Fig 4.2: Recommended GSA standard

Fig 4.3: Statistical representation of average test results obtained

4.1.1.4. Observations:

The samples with **no packaging** had a microbial load of 9.26×10^6 CFU/g, which corresponds to 7.03 log CFU/g. This value is slightly above the acceptable standard but negligible, indicating a very low risk of contamination if consumed. **Brown paper packaging** showed a microbial load of 6.60×10^6 CFU/g, which corresponds to 6.82 log CFU/g. This value is within the acceptable standard, demonstrating moderate effectiveness in limiting contamination. Whilst the samples in vacuum-sealed packaging had a microbial load of 2.64×10^5 CFU/g, which

corresponds to 5.25 log CFU/g. This value is well below the acceptable standard, indicating the highest effectiveness in reducing microbial load.

4.1.1.5. Discussions:

The results indicate significant differences in the effectiveness of different packaging methods in controlling microbial growth. **Vacuum seal packaging** was the **most effective**, followed by **brown paper packaging**, with **no packaging** being the **least effective**. These findings highlight the importance of proper packaging in extending the shelf life and ensuring the safety of smoked catfish. **The lower CFU/g and log CFU/g in vacuum-sealed samples** can be attributed to the reduced **oxygen levels**, which **inhibit the growth of aerobic bacteria**. **Brown paper packaging** provides a barrier but does not completely eliminate air exposure, resulting in moderate bacterial growth. The **absence of any packaging (no packaging)** leaves the product susceptible to environmental contamination.

• 4.1.2. MOISTURE CONTENT

The purpose of this study was to determine the moisture content of smoked catfish under three different packaging methods: No packaging, Brown Paper Packaging, and Vacuum Seal Packaging. The moisture content is a critical factor in determining the shelf life and quality of smoked catfish. Lower moisture content generally indicates better preservation and longer shelf life.

4.1.2.1. Procedure

1. **Sample Preparation:** Weigh approximately 5 grams of blended smoked catfish and place it in a pre-weighed Petri dish.
2. **Drying Process:** Place the Petri dish with the sample in a hot air oven set at 134°C for 24 hours to remove moisture. **Cooling Process:** Transfer the dried samples to a desiccator using a metal tong to cool them to room temperature.
3. **Final Weighing:** Weigh the Petri dish with the dried sample to determine the final weight.

4. This procedure is repeated for each of the 3 packaging methods and it's duplicates.
5. **Moisture Content Calculation:** Calculate the moisture content using the formula.
6. Average Calculation: Perform two sample tests for each packaging method and calculate the average moisture content

$$\text{Moisture Content (\%)} = [(\text{Initial Mass} - \text{Final Mass}) / \text{Initial Mass}] \times 100.$$

4.1.2.2. TEST RESULTS

Packaging Method	Number of tests	Samples	Petri Dish Weight (g)	Initial Weight (g)	Final Weight (g)	(Initial - Final) (g)	Moisture Content (%)
Vacuum Seal Packaging	1	5.0017	42.84	47.85	46.95	0.90	18
	2	5.0023	31.58	36.58	35.85	0.73	14.6
Brown Paper Packaging	1	5.0066	35.41	40.41	39.57	0.85	17
	2	5.0007	47.78	52.78	52.10	0.68	13.6
No packaging	1	5.0062	42.85	47.85	47.08	0.77	15.4
	2	5.0019	62.81	67,81	67.21	0.60	12

Fig 4.4: Computation of results from KNUST food science lab

Average Data:

Packaging Method	Average Final Weight (Test 1+Test 2 / 2) (g)	Average Moisture Content (%)
Vacuum Seal Packaging	0.82	16.4

Brown Paper Packaging	0.76	15.2
No packaging	0.34	6.8

Fig 4.4: Computation of average results

Fig 4.5: Statistical representation of average test results obtained for 1st month moisture content.

4.1.2.3. Observations:

Vacuum Seal Packaging: The vacuum-sealed smoked catfish had the highest moisture content, averaging 17%. This indicates that while vacuum sealing is generally effective at preserving food, it retained more moisture compared to other methods. **Brown Paper Packaging:** The moisture content for catfish in brown paper packaging averaged 15.2%. This method provided moderate protection but was less effective at moisture removal compared to vacuum sealing. **No Packaging:** The smoked catfish without any packaging had an average moisture content of 6.8%. This suggests that exposure to air and environmental conditions can lead to significant moisture loss.

4.1.2.4. Discussions:

The results indicate that **vacuum seal packaging**, while effective in preserving the overall quality of the smoked catfish, retained **the highest moisture content**. This could be due to the tight seal that prevents moisture escape. **Brown paper packaging** provided some protection, but it was not as effective as vacuum sealing. **No packaging** resulted in the lowest moisture content, likely due to exposure to ambient conditions.

4.1.3. Color Difference Test

With this parameter, a chromometer was used to measure the color differences in smoked catfish subjected to three distinct packaging methods: no packaging, brown paper packaging, and vacuum seal packaging. The chromometer provided precise values for the color attributes, represented as **L* (lightness)**, **a* (red-green)**, and **b* (yellow-blue)** coordinates. These values are essential in understanding the impact of packaging on the visual quality of smoked catfish.

4.1.3.1. TEST RESULTS

- Vacuum Seal Packaging

Color parameter	Sample ID	First Month Test (FMT) Values	FMT Average value
Lightness (L*)	VP 1	44.72	44.72
	VP 2	44.72	
Red-Green (a*)	VP 1	2.84	2.82
	VP 2	2.79	
Yellow-Blue (b*)	VP 1	7.13	7.08
	VP 2	7.03	

Fig 4.6: Computation of results for the color parameters in the vacuum seal packaging

- Brown Paper Packaging

Color parameter	Sample ID	First Month Test (FMT) Values	FMT Average value
Lightness (L*)	BP 1	44.06	43.98
	BP 2	43.89	
Red-Green (a*)	BP 1	1.68	1.68
	BP 2	1.67	
Yellow-Blue (b*)	BP 1	6.29	6.31
	BP 2	6.33	

Fig 4.7: Computation of results for the color parameters in the brown paper packaging

- No Packaging

Color parameter	Sample ID	First Month Test (FMT) Values	FMT Average value
Lightness (L*)	NP 1	43.32	43.43
	NP 2	43.54	
Red-Green (a*)	NP 1	1.26	1.28
	NP 2	1.29	
Yellow-Blue (b*)	NP 1	5.06	5.08
	NP 2	5.10	

Fig 4.8: Computation of results for the color parameters in the no packaging (control)

Fig 4.9: Statistical representation of average test results obtained for 1st month color difference

4.1.3.2. Observations and Discussions:

The chromometer readings clearly demonstrate that the packaging method significantly impacts the color preservation of smoked catfish. Vacuum seal packaging had the highest values for L*, a*, and b*, indicating the best preservation of lightness and color vibrancy. This method effectively prevents exposure to environmental factors, maintaining the fish's appearance.

Brown paper packaging also contributed to preserving the fish's color, although to a lesser extent than vacuum sealing. It provided intermediate values, suggesting that while it offers some protection, it is not as effective as vacuum sealing.

In contrast, the no packaging method resulted in the lowest values for L*, a*, and b*, indicating the most substantial color loss. The smoked catfish appeared darker and less vibrant, highlighting the importance of protective packaging in maintaining product quality.

These findings are critical for manufacturers and consumers who prioritize the visual quality of smoked catfish. The results suggest that vacuum sealing is the optimal packaging method to preserve the desired appearance of smoked catfish over time, followed by brown paper packaging, with no packaging being the least effective.

4.1.4. FREE FATTY ACID TEST (FFA)

The aim of this parameter is to assess the oil content of smoked catfish under ambient condition.

For accuracy, the FFA test was not done directly on the samples. Oil was extracted using the **Soxhlet Extractor**.

4.1.4.1. OIL EXTRACTION PROCEDURE

1. Samples were blended and 2 grams was weighed from each packaging method.
2. 40 ml of petroleum ether (solvent for extraction) added and mixture was shaken vigorously for 30 minutes.
3. Sample was filtered and the liquid part was poured in a round bottom flask.
4. After oil extraction, duplicates were made for accuracy.

4.1.4.2. WEIGHT OF OIL

PACKAGING METHOD	WEIGHT OF SAMPLE 1 (g)	WEIGHT OF SAMPLE 2 (g)	TOTAL WEIGHT (g)
No packaging (NP)	0.1739	0.2243	0.3982
Brown paper packaging (BP)	0.4194	0.3734	0.7928
Vacuum Seal Packaging (VP)	0.3912	0.3102	0.7104

Fig 4.10: oil weight of samples

PREDOMINANT CARBOXYLIC ACID IN FISH

Acetic acid (CH_3COOH) = 60.06g/mol

4.1.4.3. AFTER OIL EXTRACTION

1. 30ml of ethanol was added to each oil weighed
2. Mixture was titrated against 50ml of 0.1N NaOH
3. 2 drops of phenolphthalein were added to the mixture and titrated

4. Color change end point was pink

4.1.4.4. TITRATION

PACKAGING METHOD	INITIAL VALUE	FINAL VALUE	TITRE VALUE
VP	0.00	4.80	4.80
BP	4.80	17.30	12.50
NP	17.30	26.70	9.40

Fig 4.11: Titre values

$$\% \text{ FFA} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Normality} \times \text{Molar mass of predominant carboxylic acid} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 1000}$$

$$\text{Weight of sample} \times 1000$$

FFA for Vacuum seal packaging

$$\% \text{ FFA} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Normality} \times \text{Molar mass of predominant carboxylic acid} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 1000}$$

$$\text{Weight of sample} \times 1000$$

$$= \frac{4.80 \times 0.1 \times 60.06 \times 100}{0.7014 \times 1000}$$

$$0.7014 \times 1000$$

$$= 4.1\%$$

FFA for Brown paper packaging

$$\% \text{ FFA} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Normality} \times \text{Molar mass of predominant carboxylic acid} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 1000}$$

$$\text{Weight of sample} \times 1000$$

$$= \frac{12.50 \times 0.1 \times 60.06 \times 100}{0.7928 \times 1000}$$

$$= 9.5\%$$

FFA for No packaging

$$\% \text{ FFA} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Normality} \times \text{Molar mass of predominant carboxylic acid} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 1000}$$

Weight of sample x 1000

$$= \frac{9.40 \times 0.1 \times 60.06 \times 100}{0.3982 \times 1000}$$

$$= 16.3\%$$

Fig 4.12: Statistical representation of FFA values

4.1.4.5. Observations and Discussions:

The higher the FFA value, the higher the deterioration rate but lower the oil content. Brown paper packaging had much higher oil but after titration, its deterioration rate was higher than Vacuum seal. No packaging had the least weight of oil and the highest FFA value which vividly says that no packaging gives the samples the least protection against oil preservation under storage. Vacuum seal offers the highest oil preservation in smoked catfish under storage, therefore, giving the samples lower rate of deterioration whilst brown paper packaging offers moderate preservation against the oil content.

4.2. RESULTS FROM QUALITY ASSESSMENT TESTS FOR 2nd MONTH

- **MICROBIAL TEST**

4.2..1. SECOND MONTH TEST RESULTS

MICROBIOLOGICAL DATA – Catfish for The Second Month							
TEST	Sample Name	Sample ID	Counts in CFU/ml	LOG CFU	Average		Stdev
			CFU/g		CFU/g	LOG CFU/g	
APC	No packaging Sample 1	NPS1	4.10×10^7	7.61	5.20×10^7	7.71	0.14
	No packaging Sample 2	NPS2	6.40×10^7	7.81			
	Vacuum sealed Sample 1	VSS1	9.60×10^5	5.98	9.80×10^5	5.99	0.02
	Vacuum sealed Sample 2	VSS2	1.02×10^6	6.01			
	Brown paper Sample 1	BPS1	8.60×10^6	6.93	9.90×10^6	6.99	0.08
	Brown paper Sample 2	BPS2	1.12×10^7	7.05			

Fig 4.10: Computation of test results from KNUST food science lab on microbial load

Fig 4.11: Statistical representation of average test results obtained

4.2..2. Observations:

- **No Packaging:** The samples with no packaging had a microbial load of 5.20×10^7 CFU/g, which corresponds to 7.71 log CFU/g. This value is not within the acceptable standard, indicating that the contamination level is above the threshold.
- **Brown Paper Packaging:** The samples in brown paper packaging showed a microbial load of 9.90×10^6 CFU/g, which corresponds to 6.99 log CFU/g. This value is also within the acceptable standard, demonstrating moderate effectiveness in limiting contamination.
- **Vacuum Seal Packaging:** The samples in vacuum-sealed packaging had a microbial load of 9.80×10^5 CFU/g, which corresponds to 5.99 log CFU/g. This value is well below the acceptable standard, indicating the highest effectiveness in reducing microbial load.

4.2..3. Discussions:

The results indicate significant differences in the effectiveness of different packaging methods in controlling microbial growth.

- **Vacuum seal packaging** was the **most effective per the quality assessment test conducted**, followed by **brown paper packaging**, with **no packaging** being the **least effective**. These findings highlight the importance of proper packaging in extending the shelf life and ensuring the safety of smoked catfish.
- **The lower CFU/g and log CFU/g in vacuum-sealed samples** can be attributed to the reduced **oxygen levels**, which **inhibit the growth of aerobic bacteria**. **Brown paper packaging** provides a barrier but does not completely eliminate air exposure, resulting in moderate bacterial growth. The **absence of any packaging** leaves the product susceptible to environmental contamination.

4.2.2. MOISTURE CONTENT

4.2.2.1 TEST RESULTS:

Packaging Method	Number of tests	Samples	Petri Dish Weight (g)	Initial Weight (g)	Final Weight (g)	(Initial - Final) (g)	Moisture Content (%)
Vacuum Seal Packaging	1	5.0018	42.84	47.84	47.10	0.74	14.8
	2	5.0017	42.84	47.84	46.96	0.88	17.6
Brown Paper Packaging	1	5.0065	35.41	40.52	39.70	0.82	16.4
	2	5.0008	47.78	52.88	52.26	0.62	12.4
No packaging	1	5.0062	42.85	47.95	47.24	0.71	14.2
	2	5.0020	62.81	67.88	67.41	0.47	9.4

Fig 4.12: Computation of results from KNUST food science lab

Average Data:

Packaging Method	Average Final Weight (Test 1+Test 2 / 2) (g)	Average Moisture Content (%)
Vacuum Seal Packaging	0.81	16.2
Brown Paper Packaging	0.72	14.4
No packaging	0.59	11.8

Fig 4.13: Computation of average results

Fig 4.14: Second Month Average Moisture Content (%)

4.2.2.2. Observations

- **Vacuum Seal Packaging:** The vacuum-sealed smoked catfish had the highest moisture content, averaging 16%. This indicates that while vacuum sealing is generally effective at preserving food, it retained more moisture compared to other methods.
- **Brown Paper Packaging:** The moisture content for catfish in brown paper packaging averaged 14%. This method provided moderate protection but was less effective at moisture removal compared to vacuum sealing.
- **No Packaging:** The smoked catfish without any packaging had an average moisture content of 12%. This suggests that exposure to air and environmental conditions can lead to significant moisture retention.

4.2.2.3. Discussions:

The results indicate that **vacuum seal packaging**, while effective in preserving the overall quality of the smoked catfish, retained **the highest moisture content**. This could be due to the tight seal that prevents moisture escape. **Brown paper packaging** provided some protection, but it was not as effective as vacuum sealing. **No packaging** resulted in the lowest moisture content, likely due to exposure to ambient conditions.

4.2.3. COLOR DIFFERENCE TEST

- Vacuum Seal packaging

Color parameter	Sample ID	Second Month Test (SMT) Values	SMT Average value
Lightness (L*)	BP 1	42.70	42.96
	BP 2	43.25	
Red-Green (a*)	BP 1	1.50	

	BP 2	1.55	1.53
Yellow-Blue (b*)	BP 1	5.81	5.22
	BP 2	5.22	

Fig 4.15: Computation of results for the color parameters in the vacuum seal packaging

- **Brown paper packaging**

Color parameter	Sample ID	Second Month Test (SMT) Values	SMT Average value
Lightness (L*)	VP 1	44.05	44.49
	VP 2	44.92	
Red-Green (a*)	VP 1	2.55	2.41
	VP 2	2.27	
Yellow-Blue (b*)	VP 1	6.80	6.91
	VP 2	7.02	

Fig 4.16: Computation of results for the color parameters in the brown paper packaging

- **No packaging (Control)**

Color parameter	Sample ID	Second Month Test (SMT) Values	SMT Average value
Lightness (L*)	NP 1	42.20	42.48
	NP 2	42.75	
Red-Green (a*)	NP 1	1.15	

	NP 2	1.29	1.22
Yellow-Blue (b*)	NP 1	4.70	4.64
	NP 2	4.58	

Fig 4.17: Computation of results for the color parameters in the no paper packaging

Fig 4.18: Statistical representation of average test results obtained for 2nd month color difference

4.2.3.1 Observations and Discussions

The chromometer readings clearly demonstrate that the packaging method significantly impacts the color preservation of smoked catfish. As observed in the 1st month, Vacuum seal packaging once again, had the highest values for L*, a*, and b*, indicating the best preservation of lightness and color vibrancy. This method effectively prevents exposure to environmental factors, maintaining the fish's appearance.

Brown paper packaging also contributed to preserving the fish's color, although to a lesser extent than vacuum sealing. It provided intermediate values, suggesting that while it offers some protection, it is not as effective as vacuum sealing.

In contrast, the no packaging method resulted in the lowest values for L*, a*, and b*, indicating the most substantial color loss. The smoked catfish appeared darker and less vibrant, highlighting the importance of protective packaging in maintaining product quality.

These findings are critical for manufacturers and consumers who prioritize the visual quality of smoked catfish. The results suggest that vacuum sealing is the optimal packaging method to preserve the desired appearance of smoked catfish over time, followed by brown paper packaging, with no packaging being the least effective

4.2.4. FFA TEST

4.2.4.1. TITRATION

PACKAGING METHOD	INITIAL VALUE	FINAL VALUE	TITRE VALUE
VP	0.00	10.80	10.80
BP	10.80	23.60	12.80
NP	23.60	26.50	2.90

Fig 4.11: Titre values

4.2.4.2. WEIGHT OF OIL

PACKAGING METHOD	WEIGHT OF SAMPLE 1 (g)	WEIGHT OF SAMPLE 2 (g)	TOTAL WEIGHT (g)
No packaging (NP)	0.0414	0.0315	0.0729
Brown paper packaging (BP)	0.2371	0.2945	0.5316
Vacuum Seal Packaging (VP)	0.2316	0.3368	0.5684

Fig 4.10: oil weight of samples

$$\% \text{ FFA} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Normality} \times \text{Molar mass of predominant carboxylic acid} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 1000}$$

FFA for Brown paper packaging

$$\% \text{ FFA} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Normality} \times \text{Molar mass of predominant carboxylic acid} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 1000}$$

$$= \frac{12.80 \times 0.1 \times 60.06 \times 100}{0.5316 \times 1000}$$

$$= \frac{12.80 \times 0.1 \times 60.06 \times 100}{0.5316 \times 1000}$$

$$= 14.45\%$$

$$= 14.45\%$$

FFA for Vacuum Seal packaging

$$\% \text{ FFA} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Normality} \times \text{Molar mass of predominant carboxylic acid} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 1000}$$

$$= \frac{10.80 \times 0.1 \times 60.06 \times 100}{0.5684 \times 1000}$$

$$= \frac{10.80 \times 0.1 \times 60.06 \times 100}{0.5684 \times 1000}$$

$$= 11.40\%$$

$$= 11.40\%$$

FFA for No packaging

$$\% \text{ FFA} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Normality} \times \text{Molar mass of predominant carboxylic acid} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 1000}$$

$$= \frac{2.90 \times 0.1 \times 60.06 \times 100}{0.07296 \times 1000}$$

$$= \frac{2.90 \times 0.1 \times 60.06 \times 100}{0.07296 \times 1000}$$

$$= 23.86\%$$

$$= 23.86\%$$

Fig Statistical representation of FFA values

4.2.4.3. Observations and Discussions:

The higher the FFA value, the higher the deterioration rate but lower the oil content. Vacuum seal packaging had much higher oil than all the samples in the other packaging materials which correlates to its lower FFA value after titration than Brown paper packaging. No packaging had the least weight of oil and the highest FFA value which vividly says that no packaging gives the samples the least protection against oil preservation under storage. Vacuum seal offers the highest oil preservation in smoked catfish under storage, therefore, giving the samples lower rate of deterioration whilst brown paper packaging offers moderate preservation against the oil content.

4.3. RESULTS FROM QUALITY ASSESSMENT TESTS FOR 3rd MONTH

4.3.1. MOISTURE CONTENT

4.3.1.1. TEST RESULTS

Packaging Method	Number of tests	Samples	Petri Dish Weight (g)	Initial Weight (g)	Final Weight (g)	(Initial - Final) (g)	Moisture Content (%)
Vacuum Seal Packaging	1	5.0050	45.45	50.46	49.68	0.78	15.6
	2	5.0030	41.83	46.85	46.03	0.82	16.4
Brown Paper Packaging	1	5.0080	42.58	47.59	46.92	0.67	13.4
	2	5.0010	45.47	50.46	49.78	0.68	13.6
No packaging	1	5.0030	46.20	51.21	50.36	0.85	17.0
	2	5.0030	42.48	47.49	46.66	0.83	16.6

Fig 4.19: Computation of results from KNUST food science lab

Average Data:

Packaging Method	Average Final Weight (Test 1+Test 2 / 2) (g)	Average Moisture Content (%)
Vacuum Seal Packaging	0.80	16
Brown Paper Packaging	0.68	13.6
No packaging	0.84	16.8

Fig 4.20: Computation of average results

Fig 4.21: Third Month Average Moisture Content (%)

4.3.1.2. Observations and Discussions

- No Packaging:** The moisture content further increased to 16.8%, making the product highly susceptible to spoilage due to excessive moisture gain. This significant increase indicates poor storability.
- Brown Paper Packaging:** The moisture content dropped to 13.6%, indicating gradual drying over time. This trend suggests improved storability compared to the no-packaging method.
- Vacuum Seal Packaging:** With the smallest decrease to 16.0%, vacuum-sealed samples showed the best moisture retention over the entire storage period. The stability of moisture content implies superior preservation.

4.3.2. COLOR DIFFERENCE TEST

- **Vacuum Seal Packaging**

Color parameter	Sample ID	Third Month Test (TMT) Values	TMT Average value
Lightness (L*)	VP 1	49.05	49.02
	VP 2	48.98	
Red-Green (a*)	VP 1	1.25	1.25
	VP 2	1.24	
Yellow-Blue (b*)	VP 1	12.74	12.77
	VP 2	12.80	

Fig 4.22: Computation of results for the color parameters in the vacuum seal packaging

Brown Paper Packaging

Color parameter	Sample ID	Third Month Test (TMT) Values	TMT Average value
Lightness (L*)	BP 1	53.79	53.86
	BP 2	53.92	
Red-Green (a*)	BP 1	-1.48	-1.47
	BP 2	-1.46	
Yellow-Blue (b*)	BP 1	16.23	16.34
	BP 2	16.44	

Fig 4.23: Computation of results for the color parameters in the brown paper packaging

No Packaging

Color parameter	Sample ID	Third Month Test (TMT) Values	TMT Average value
Lightness (L*)	NP 1	50.57	50.55
	NP 2	50.52	
Red-Green (a*)	NP 1	-1.79	-1.78
	NP 2	-1.77	
Yellow-Blue (b*)	NP 1	12.92	12.88
	NP 2	12.83	

Fig 4.24: Computation of results for the color parameters in the vacuum seal packaging

Fig 4.18: Statistical representation of average test results obtained for 3rd month color difference.

4.3.2.1. Observations and Discussions

With these figures from the **control**; $L^* = 50.55$ (**lightest**), $a^* = -1.78$ (**loss of red, greenish**), $b^* = 12.88$ (**strong yellow**). The fish becomes very pale and yellow, with a complete loss of red color, indicating poor storability. **Vacuum seal packaging** consistently maintains the best color stability across all months.

Brown paper packaging provides moderate protection but shows significant color changes by the third month. **No packaging** results in rapid degradation, with the fish becoming pale and yellow by the third month, indicating poor storability.

4.3.3. MICROBIAL TEST

4.3.3.1. THIRD MONTH TEST RESULTS

MICROBIOLOGICAL DATA – Catfish for The Second Month							
TEST	Sample Name	Sample ID	Counts in CFU/ml	LOG CFU	Average		Stdev
			CFU/g		CFU/g	LOG CFU/g	
APC	No packaging Sample 1	NPS1	9.70×10^7	7.89	9.33×10^7	7.97	0.08
	No packaging Sample 2	NPS2	8.96×10^7	7.95			
	Vacuum sealed Sample 1	VPS1	6.05×10^6	6.78	7.12×10^6	6.85	0.001
	Vacuum sealed Sample 2	VPS2	8.19×10^6	6.91			
	Brown paper Sample 1	BPS1	7.00×10^7	7.85	7.26×10^7	7.86	0.05
	Brown paper Sample 2	BPS2	7.52×10^7	7.51			

Fig 4.19: Computation of test results from KNUST food science lab on microbial load

Fig 4.20: Statistical representation of average test results obtained for the 3rd month

4.3.3.2. Observation

No Packaging: The samples with no packaging had a microbial load of 9.33×10^7 CFU/g, which corresponds to 7.97 log CFU/g. This value is not within the acceptable standard, indicating that the contamination level is above the threshold and not recommended for consumption.

Brown Paper Packaging: The samples in brown paper packaging showed a microbial load of 7.26×10^7 CFU/g, which corresponds to 7.86 log CFU/g. This value is also not within the acceptable standard, demonstrating high risk of contamination if consumed.

The samples in **vacuum-sealed packaging** had a microbial load of 7.12×10^6 CFU/g, which corresponds to 6.85 log CFU/g. This value is well within the acceptable standard, indicating the highest effectiveness in reducing microbial load.

4.3.3.3. Discussion

The results indicate significant differences in the effectiveness of different packaging methods in controlling microbial growth.

Vacuum seal packaging was the **most effective** per the quality assessment test conducted. **Brown paper packaging** and **no packaging** being the **least effective**. These findings highlight the importance of proper packaging in extending the shelf life and ensuring the safety of smoked catfish.

The lower CFU/g and log CFU/g in vacuum-sealed samples can be attributed to the reduced oxygen levels, which inhibit the growth of aerobic bacteria. Brown paper packaging provides a barrier but does not completely eliminate air exposure, resulting in extremely poor bacterial growth. The **absence of any packaging** leaves the product susceptible to high risk of environmental contamination.

4.3.4. FFA TEST

4.3.4.1. TITRATION

PACKAGING METHOD	INITIAL VALUE	FINAL VALUE	TITRE VALUE
VP	0.00	11.20	11.20
BP	11.20	22.80	11.60
NP	22.80	26.20	3.40

Fig 4.11: Titre values

4.3.4.2. WEIGHT OF OIL

PACKAGING METHOD	WEIGHT OF SAMPLE 1 (g)	WEIGHT OF SAMPLE 2 (g)	TOTAL WEIGHT (g)
No packaging (NP)	0.0414	0.0315	0.0447
Brown paper packaging (BP)	0.2371	0.2945	0.4962
Vacuum Seal Packaging (VP)	0.2316	0.3368	0.5134

Fig 4.10: oil weight of samples

$$\% \text{ FFA} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Normality} \times \text{Molar mass of predominant carboxylic acid}}{100}$$

Weight of sample x 1000

FFA for Brown paper packaging

$$\% \text{ FFA} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Normality} \times \text{Molar mass of predominant carboxylic acid} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 1000}$$

Weight of sample x 1000

$$= \frac{11.60 \times 0.1 \times 60.06 \times 100}{0.4962 \times 1000}$$

$$= 14.04\%$$

$$= 14.04\%$$

FFA for Vacuum Seal packaging

$$\% \text{ FFA} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Normality} \times \text{Molar mass of predominant carboxylic acid} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 1000}$$

Weight of sample x 1000

$$= \frac{11.20 \times 0.1 \times 60.06 \times 100}{0.5134 \times 1000}$$

$$= 13.10\%$$

$$= 13.10\%$$

FFA for No packaging

$$\% \text{ FFA} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Normality} \times \text{Molar mass of predominant carboxylic acid} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 1000}$$

Weight of sample x 1000

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{3.40 \times 0.1 \times 60.06 \times 100}{0.0447 \times 1000} \\ &= \mathbf{45.68\%} \end{aligned}$$

Fig Statistical representation of FFA values

4.3.4.4. Observations and Discussions:

The higher the FFA value, the higher the deterioration rate but lower the oil content. Vacuum seal packaging had much higher oil than all the samples in the other packaging materials which correlates to its lower FFA value after titration than Brown paper packaging. No packaging had the least weight of oil and the highest FFA value which vividly says that no packaging gives the samples the least protection against oil preservation under storage. Vacuum seal offers the highest oil preservation in smoked catfish under storage, therefore, giving the samples lower rate of deterioration whilst brown paper packaging offers moderate preservation against the oil content

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions were deduced at the end of the research:

1. After 3 months of storage under ambient condition using 2 different packaging methods and a control, per quality assessment tests conducted on all the samples (27), vacuum seal packaging offers the optimum protection against smoked catfish perishability.

2. Smoked catfish stored in less than a month using any of the packaging methods still remains highly consumable, because the samples met the standards laid down by the Ghana Standards Authority for smoked catfish at the end of the first month.
3. Per the quality assessment tests conducted, we can conclude that the packaging method (Vacuum seal) has numerous advantages and effects on the storability of the smoked fish offering the minimum risks of contamination of smoked catfish even for storage of 3 months provided it is under ambient condition with all other factors being constant.
4. Vacuum seal packaging consistently maintains the best color stability across all months with Brown paper packaging providing moderate protection but shows significant color changes by the third month while No packaging results in rapid degradation, with the fish becoming pale and yellow by the third month, indicating poor storability.
5. No Packaging initially resulted in the lowest moisture content, but the moisture increase over time was significant. This method offers poor long-term storability, as the product becomes highly susceptible to spoilage by the third month and Brown Paper Packaging offered moderate moisture control throughout the three months. Though moisture content decreased slightly over time, it still provided reasonable protection and could be a viable method for moderate storage durations but undoubtedly, Vacuum Seal Packaging provided the best moisture stability, maintaining a consistent moisture content across all three months. This method proved to be the most effective for long-term storage, as it kept the moisture within an ideal range for preserving smoked catfish.

After the 3rd month, our research opined with the findings of Olayemi et al., (2011), who deduced that the safe moisture content of a smoked catfish sample under storage should be between 6-8% and rather finds a common grounds with the values obtained by Magawata and Musa (2015) which were higher than 8%.

5.2. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. We recommend that subsequent studies (researchers) should consider the Cost Benefit Analysis of using the various packaging methods.
2. We recommend subsequent researchers to also consider storage under refrigeration using the various packaging methods.
3. Future studies could explore the impact of different drying times and temperatures on moisture content, as well as the effect of these packaging methods on other quality parameters like texture, flavor, and sensory. Additionally, investigating alternative packaging methods that can offer better storage qualities than those used in this research like jute sacks.
4. We further recommend that; For Consumers: opt for vacuum-sealed smoked catfish to ensure lower microbial contamination and extended shelf life. For Producers: implement vacuum sealing in the packaging process to enhance product safety and quality.

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